

WORD-FORMATION OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ITS ROLE IN ENLARGING LEXICAL RESOURCE

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ANNOTATION

Modern English is distinguished by its great ability to form new vocabulary units. Most new formations are created with the help of those word-building methods and means that a particular language has. This article will represent the main ways of word formation in modern English: affixation, conversion and compounding are used now and have been used in the language for many years. However, not all of them are used to the same extent, and the share of each method in the word-formation process is not the same.

Key words: *vocabulary, word-formation, new formation, affixation, conversion, compounding.*

Language is a means of forming and collecting ideas as a reflection of reality and exchanging them throughout life. It has the quality of sociability, which is inseparably linked with people, and it develops due to society develops. The lexical resource of the word is constantly changing.

For knowledge of a foreign language, the richness of the vocabulary is no less important than the understanding of grammar. The more words a person owns, the freer he feels in a foreign language environment.

The variety of vocabulary is largely determined by the richness of word formation in the English language. The construction of new words is based on general principles. And the one who knows these principles feels much more confident among unfamiliar vocabulary.

Nowadays, the terms ‘word formation’ does not have a universally accepted usage and a clear meaning. It is sometimes referred to all processes connected with changing the form of the word by, for example, affixation, which is a matter of morphology.[2]

In its wider sense word formation denotes the processes of creation of new lexical units. Although it seems that the difference between morphological change of a word and creation of a new term is quite easy to perceive, there is sometimes a dispute as to whether blending is still a morphological change or making a new word. There are, of course, numerous word formation processes that do not arouse any controversies and are very similar in the majority of languages.

Problem of word formation in the English language was deeply studied by the authors of textbooks on the lexicology of the English language, such as G.B.Antrushina.V, I.V.Arnold, T.I.Arbekova, V.V.Eliseeva, S.G.Kibasova, A.N.Ilyina, Z.A. Kharitonchik.

New words are created in 3 basic ways in the English language:

- I. *Affixing*– word formation using prefixes and suffixes.
- II. *conversion*– the transformation from one part of speech to another.
- III. *compounding*– adding two or more roots.

I. According to V.V. Eliseeva, one of the most productive ways of word formation in modern English is *affixation*, which consists in attaching affixes to roots or stems[3].

The word-formation structure of a newly formed word presupposes the presence of three obligatory components: a root or stem, an affix, and a model by which the affix is attached to the generating stem. The derived word is the result of the interaction of these three components. It must be taken into account that the affix realizes its meaning not in isolation, but in combination with the base word. In terms of structure, word-formation bases are divided into free and connected.

Free stems coincide with the minimal structure of the word, and are characterized by the absence of derivational affixes. They can coincide with the root morpheme (day, wide, work), be derivative in structure (daily, widen, worker) or complex (brainstorm, businessman, teamwork). In all these cases, free stems coincide with morphological roots and may also coincide with word forms and phrases. Associated stems, unlike free stems, form the so-called word-building paradigms. For instance, in the words: *actor*, *active*, *activity*, *activate*, *action*, the free stem act is distinguished in the first four words and the associated stem act- in the word action [1].

In modern English affixation is represented in two ways: suffixation and prefixation. As a word-formation means, suffixation consists in attaching suffixes to roots and stems. There are quite a few criteria for describing and classifying word-forming suffixes.

The main types of their classification according to A.N. Ilina are the following:

1. Classification of suffixes depends on the part of speech to which the derived word belongs. When attached to the base word, it performs a categorical function, while transferring the derived word to another part of speech. In this classification, the following types of suffixes are distinguished:

- a) Nominal suffixes - suffixes that form nouns from different stems;
- b) Adjective suffixes - suffixes that form adjectives from different stems;
- c) Verbal suffixes - suffixes that form verbs from different stems;
- d) Adverbial suffixes - suffixes that form adverbs from different stems.

2. Classification of word-building suffixes depending on the part of speech to which the original word belongs:

- a) Nominative suffixes- suffixes that join the stems of nouns;
- b) Verbal suffixes- suffixes that combine with the stems of verbs;
- c) Adjective suffixes- suffixes that join the stems of adjectives.

3. Semantic classification based on the generality of the abstract categorical meaning inherent in the word-forming suffix. For example, among the nominal suffixes, the following semantic classes can be distinguished:

- a) Collective meaning suffixes: -age, -dom (luggage, freedom, boredom);
- b) Agentive suffixes -ant, -er, -ee, -ess, -eer (assistant, employer, player, employee, actress, engineer,);
- c) Suffixes, defining national or geographic attachment: -ian, -ese (Canadian, Chinese);
- d) Diminutive suffixes: -ie, -let, -ling, -ette (birdie, booklet, duckling, kitchenette).

4. There are also native English and borrowed word-building suffixes.

5. The classification of derivational suffixes in terms of their productivity distinguishes between "live" and "dead" suffixes. "Live" suffixes include those suffixes that can be easily separated from the stem. As for the "dead" suffixes, these suffixes are completely out of use and therefore are perceived as an indivisible part of the word. As academician V.V. Vinogradov notes, affixes that have lost their meaning, become unproductive and are perceived only as a sign of one or another part of speech, convey being affixes and only potentially retain the property of being distinguished.

There are some productive affixes:

Noun-forming suffixes	-er (<i>trainer, leader</i>), -ing (<i>dying, building</i>), -ness (<i>coldness, fairness</i>), -ism (<i>materialism</i>), -ist (<i>impressionist</i>)
Adjective-forming suffixes	-y (<i>angry, merry</i>), -ish (<i>oldish, lookish</i>), -ed (<i>learned</i>), -able (<i>capable</i>)
Adverb-forming suffixes	-ly (<i>coldly, simply</i>)
Verb-forming suffixes	-ize/-ise (<i>realize</i>)
Prefixes	un- (<i>unhappy</i>), re- (<i>reconstruct</i>), dis- (<i>disappoint</i>)

There are some non-productive affixes:

Noun-forming suffixes	-th (<i>growth</i>), -hood (<i>childhood</i>)
Adjective-forming suffixes	-ly (<i>early</i>), -some , -en , -ous (<i>friendly</i>)
Verb-forming suffix	-en (<i>shorten</i>)

II. Conversion (zero derivation, root formation, functional change) is the process of coining a new word in a different part of speech and with different distribution characteristics but without adding any derivative element, so that the basic form of the original and the basic form of derived words are homonymous. This phenomenon can be illustrated by the following cases: work – to work, love – to love, water – to water.

Referring to V.V. Eliseev, conversion is one of the main productive ways to replenish the vocabulary of modern English [3].

The reason for such a wide distribution of conversion is the almost complete absence of morphological indicators of parts of speech.

In other words, the root, stem and grammatical form of a word can match in form, sound and spelling. Only external indicators, such as the article, help determine the meaning and function of a word in a sentence. When a new word is created by conversion with the original root stem, the following changes occur:

Firstly, the new word receives all the endings that serve to form grammatical forms in the new part of speech;

Secondly, the new word acquires a different syntactic function and compatibility;

Thirdly, the new word acquires a new lexical and grammatical meaning.

The last change is due to the fact that in the process of forming a new word by conversion, the categorical meaning of the original stem changes.

In other words, a new word is included in a new paradigm and is characterized by new grammatical categories. In addition, the result of the conversion is the homonymy of the main forms of the derived word and the original word, that the appearance of language units that coincide in form, sound and spelling, but have different meanings and belong to different parts of speech.

There are some examples of conversion:

Noun to verb: Don't *butter* the bread for me. I prefer jam.

Verb to noun: He scored a *hit* in his first shot; He used some *cheats* in the computer game to make him win easier.

Adjective to noun: I am one of the *regulars* at the pubs; Stop shouting and running around like a *crazy*.

Adjective to verb: Can you *empty* the bin for me, please?

III. Compounding, also called *composition*, is when two or more words are combined together to form a new word. For example, the word *underground* is a combination of the words *under* and *ground*. In English, *compounding* is used to form words belonging to four common parts of speech: nouns, verbs, adjectives, and adverbs.

Most of the time, compounding creates a word or phrase that means something different than the meanings of the words used as “ingredients.” For example, the word *bluebird* refers to specific species of songbirds whereas the separate words *blue bird* refers to any bird with blue feathers. As another example, the

adjective *old school* refers to supporting traditional methods or values and doesn't refer to ancient scholarly buildings.

In conclusion, there are diversity of word formation processes that were mentioned above. These processes create new words and puts them in different grammatical categories, as well as creates new meanings to some words.

We came to the conclusion that affix formations are the most productive, composition, conversion, since they have come a long way in the history of the English language.

REFERENCES

1. Amosova N.N (1956) *“Etimologicheskie osnovi slovarnogo sostava sovremennogo angliyskogo yazika”* – Moscow, 35.
2. Antrushina G.B 2007 *“Leksikologiya angliyskogo yazika”* – Drofa, 8.
3. Eliseeva V.V (2003) *“Leksikologiya angliyskogo yazika”* HomeEnglish, 12-20.
4. Ingo Plag (2003) *“Word Formation in English, Word Formation”* –Cambridge University Press.
5. Karashuk P.M (1977) *“Slovoobrazovatel'naya kategoriya angliyskogo yazika”*.
6. Leonhard Lipca (2002) *“English Lexicology: Lexical Structure, Word Semantics & Word-formation, Lexicology”*.
7. Vinogradov V (1952) *“Slovoobrazovatel'nie v ego otnoshenii k gramatike i leksikologii”* .
8. www.wikipedia.com